

Electrical Conduction Mechanisms in Insulators. Part-II. Regenerated Cellulose Films

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Commercially available transparent protective films known as cellophane are formed when viscose is forced through a narrow slit, the cellulose being regenerated as the films can be softened by glycerol. These films are of interest since they are used as dielectrics.

A typical current-voltage curve for cellophane films is shown in Fig. 1. Similar curves were obtained for other samples of varying thickness (20–240 μm). Reversing the polarity of the electrodes did not affect the characteristics.

Plot of $\log J$ against $F^{1/2}$ were linear, where J is the current density and F the field. A slight curvature is observed at low fields. The slopes are tabulated in Table 1.

Fig. 1. (J vs V) Characteristics for cellulose films

TABLE 1—SLOPES AND WORK FUNCTIONS				
Thickness μm	Slope of $\log J$ - $F^{1/2}$ plot $(\text{V}/\text{cm})^{-1/2}$	Slope of $\log I/T^2$ - $1/T$ plot at 900 V in K $\times 10^3$	ϕ from $\log I$ - $V^{1/2}$ plot	ϕ from $\log I/T^2$ - $1/T$ plot
240	1.97	7.99	0.96	0.83
200	1.92	7.96	0.92	0.81
180	2.14	7.93	0.89	0.78

Plots of $\log J$ - $V^{1/2}$ at different temperatures for a sample of 200 μm thickness are shown in Fig. 2, V being the applied voltage. The curves suggest a strong temperature dependence. The $\log J$ - $\log V$ plots obtained for these films show a continuous variation and do not yield any linear region apart from the Ohm's law region. These characteristics suggest Schottky emission mechanism. This is a

Fig. 2 ($\log J$ - $V^{1/2}$) Curves for cellulose.

type of electron emission from a metal at a negative potential in the presence of an applied field which lowers the barrier height¹. The force, on an electron at a distance x from the surface of an uncharged metal, where x is much greater than the interaction distance but much less than the surface dimensions is $f = -e^2/4\epsilon x^2$, where e is the electronic charge and ϵ the dielectric constant.

The potential energy may be assumed to have the form,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(x) &= (-e^2/4\epsilon x) - (e^2/\phi) \text{ for } x \geq 0 \\ \text{and} \quad &= -\phi \quad \text{for } x \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

For a negatively charged metal, the potential energy is increased by the term $e\phi = -Fex$. Therefore, the total potential energy,

$$\phi_t = (-e^2/4\epsilon x + e^2/\phi) - Fex \text{ for } x \geq 0$$

The maximum value of ϕ_t from differentiation is found to be $\phi_m = (-F^{1/2} e^{3/2})/2\epsilon^{1/2}$

The Schottky emission mechanism can be characterised by an equation of the type²

$$I = \alpha \exp(\beta V^{1/2})$$

The constants in the above expression are

$$\beta = (e^3/\epsilon s)^{1/2}/kT \text{ and } \alpha = AT^2 \exp(-\phi/kT)$$

where s is the thickness of the insulator, k the Boltzmann constant, A the Richardson constant and T the absolute temperature.

The plot of $\log I$ versus $V^{1/2}$ is a straight line.

The intercept on the axis of $\log I$ gives the value of α . Taking the value of A as $120 \text{ A cm}^{-2} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-2}$, the values of ϕ are obtained (Table 1). Table 1 also includes the values of ϕ obtained from the plot of $\log I/T^2$ vs $1/T$. The values differ slightly, for A and ϵ being functions of temperature, the work function ϕ depends on space charge effects as well as on field strengths³.

The study concludes that regenerated cellulose acetate films exhibit Schottky emission at field strengths greater than 4 MV m^{-1} .

Experimental

Transparent cellophane sheets (Travancore Rayons Ltd.) of varying thickness (20–240 μm) were used. The experimental cell used has been described in an earlier communication⁴. A circle of the same diameter as the fixed electrode was cut from each of the cellophane sheets. The samples were then dipped into conductivity water and then dried in an air-oven at 100° . The samples were then carefully placed in the cell. Ten samples of varying thickness (20–240 μm) were used.

References

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